

Criteria for prioritizing climate & ocean data preservation

Sep 25, 2025 || version 1.0

Kate Wing, <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-0904-2886>

Rachael E. Blake, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0847-9100>

Steve Diggs, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3814-6104>

Joseph Gum, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3045-0593>

Julia Stewart Lowndes <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1682-3872>

Mark Parsons, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7723-0950>

Yuhan Douglas Rao <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6850-3403>

Background

An informal group of climate & ocean data experts hosted a workshop on identifying data preservation priorities at the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) July 2025 Summer meeting. The discussion emerged from several overlapping efforts:

1. An active NASEM project on [data stewardship and earth observing systems](#). Participants who had engaged with the expert process felt the project would benefit from more perspectives from data managers as well as a way to think about tradeoffs and hard decisions.
2. The [Repository Crisis Scorecard](#) created by the ESIP Sustainable Data Management Cluster. This tool for assessing risks at the repository level could be adapted to look at dataset risks. Several of the scorecard authors contributed to the draft criteria and joined the July discussion.
3. Ongoing data resilience efforts. Many of the session participants were involved in data preservation independently or through multi-institutional networks. Often, they were asked as an “ocean/climate subject matter expert” to comment on the resilience or importance of a specific dataset. Guidance on how to evaluate these factors would be helpful.

At the workshop, we set up a 3 x 3 matrix (high / medium / low) where one axis was the impact or importance of the data and the other axis was the level of risk of data loss. We prepopulated the rows and columns with draft prioritization criteria drawn from work already done by ESIP as well as examples from agencies and research institutions. We deliberately chose to separate assessing risk and importance and start with these two aspects independently, before looking at capacity needs and implementation steps, such as the staff, storage, and funding needed to preserve the data. Preservation activities will necessarily be constrained by available resources, and the goal of this framework was to offer guidance on where to invest those resources.

During the workshop, participants both provided feedback on the draft criteria and ranked datasets they were familiar with to test the framework. The list below reflects a synthesis of that discussion. The workshop participants emphasized that preserving, moving, and rehosting data so it can be discovered and used is no small task. Where existing data stewards can invest in thorough documentation in advance of any changes to data infrastructure this will benefit future data rehosting, if necessary, as well as support the overall FAIRness of the data.

How to use these criteria

The criteria are designed to fit into a table where datasets are categorized by their general scores against the Risk and Impact criteria. A data creator, owner, manager, or steward can individually assess a dataset against each criterion in the list below and determine if it fits in the High, Medium or Low section for each axis. The results of that assessment can be used in data preservation discussions with internal teams and external partners.

		Risk		
		High	Medium	Low
Impact	High	<i>Dataset A</i>		
	Medium		<i>Dataset D</i>	
	Low		<i>Dataset C</i>	<i>Dataset B</i>

The authors are interested in feedback from people who have tested out the framework and criteria and plan to update this document. Please contact the lead author (kate@intertidal.agency) with comments.

Prioritization criteria

Data Impact	Rating
Calibration/Validation data with proper documentation	High
Data associated with manuscripts ready to submit to journals	High
Data products produced for known community/users where loss would have high impact on those users	High
Digital audio or video recordings of environmental phenomena with proper documentation	High
Earth systems and weather model output that cannot be reproduced	High
Model code base	High
Original observations of the earth with proper documentation	High
Ongoing time-series where gaps in data collection significantly degrade data value or utility	Medium
Laboratory, mesocosm, and field experiments	Medium
Social, behavioral, human use, cultural, historical, and economic data	Medium
Software used to produce, analyze or visualize data	Medium
Experimental model data/results	Low
Intermediate data products between raw and final data products	Low
Reproducible model results	Low

Data Risk	Rating
Data only stored locally on laptops, hard drives, etc. (no archive/single access point)	High
Data that is not systematically backed-up and/or subject to single point loss	High
Likely loss of key data steward and/or funding in the next X amount of time	Medium
Back-ups accessible to others (e.g. institutional storage) but not public/open	Medium
Data that do not have a minimum level of metadata or documentation needed for independent understanding of the data, its location, lineage or management. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If documentation can and will be created - Medium • Irreproducible historic and analog datasets, other artifacts that lack digital documentation - High 	Medium to High
Data stored on public repository	Low